

KARTOSHKA VA SABZAVOT EKINLARIDAGI GULLI PARAZIT BEGONA O‘TLARGA QARSHI GERBITSIDLARNI QO‘LLASHNING SAMARADORLIGI

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ANNOTATSIYA

Sabzavotlar va kartoshka ekin maydonlarida tarqalgan begona o‘tlar va gulli parazitlarning zararini, begona o‘tlar va gulli parazitlarini urug‘larini unib chiqishi va bu jarayonga ta‘sir qiluvchi omillarni o‘rganish, gerbitsidlarning turi va sarflash me‘yorlari bo‘yicha ma‘lumotlar keltirilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Pomidor, kartoshka, piyoz, sabzi, zarpechak, qarshi kurash, pivot 10 % s.e.k, treflan, 24 % k., gerbitsid, iqdiodiy samaradorlik.

ABSTRACT:

The study of the harm of weeds and flower parasites scattered in vegetable and potato crop fields, the germination of seeds of weeds and flower parasites and the factors affecting this process, data on the type of herbicides and spending standards are presented.

Key words: Tomato, potatoes, onion, carrots, zarpechak, pivot 10% s.e.k, treflan, 24% k., herbicide, economic efficiency.

KIRISH: Dunyodagi ko‘plab mamlakatlarda, jumladan, Xitoyda begona o‘tlarga qarshi tuproqqa yuza ishlov berish va gerbitsidlarni kartoshka va sabzavotlarni ekish bilan birga, yoki vegetatsiya davrida qo‘llash, AQSh va Hindistonda 2-3 yilda bir marta chuqur (32-35 sm) shudgorlash va gerbitsidlarni ekishdan oldin, ekish bilan birga va sabzavotlarning vegetatsiya davrida ishlatish yaxshi natija berishi aniqlangan. Kartoshka va sabzavot yetishtiriladigan dalalarning begona o‘tlardan toza bo‘lishida gerbitsidlarni foydalanish eng samarali usul bo‘lib, ekinlarning rivojlanishi uchun

qulay sharoit yaratadi hamda hosildorlikni oshirishni ta'minlaydi. Lekin bir dalada bir gerbitsidni surunkasiga qo'llash shu preparatga chidamli bo'lgan begona o't turlarini ko'payib ketishiga olib keladi. Shundan kelib chiqqan holda Toshkent viloyati sharoitida turoqqa ishlov berish usullari va yangi gerbitsidlarni qo'llash juda dolzarb masalalardan hisoblanadi.

Muammoning o'rganilganlik darajasi: Begona o'tlarga qarshi agrotexnik (V.Kondratyuk, Z.Tursunxo'jaev, M.Muhammadjonov, Q.Mirzajonov, B.Baxromov, F.Hasanova) va kimyoviy kurash tadbirlarini (B.Aleev, M.Lofovatskaya, I.Libershteyn, A.Jarasov, J.Jarovov, N.Xalilov, T.Xodjaqulov, A.Sagdullaev, M.Shodmanov, B.Nasirov, N.Turdieva, A.Yuldashev, S.Sullieva) ishlab chiqish bo'yicha bir qator tadqiqotlar o'tkazilgan.

Sabzavotlar va kartoshka ekin maydonlarida tarqalgan begona o'tlar va gulli parazitlarning zararini, begona o'tlar va gulli parazitlarini urug'larini unib chiqishi va bu jarayonga ta'sir qiluvchi omillarni o'rganish, gerbitsidlarning turi va sarflash me'yorlari ishlab chiqish dolzarbdir.

TADQIQOT NATIJALARI.

Pomidor, kartoshka, piyoz, sabzida parazitlik qiladigan zarpechak turlariga qarshi kichik tajriba maydonchalarida va ishlab chiqarish sharoitida Pivot 10 % s.e.k. gerbitsidi 0,5 l/ga, 1 l/ga, 1,5 l/ga va etalon sifatida olingan Treflan, 24 % k.e. gerbitsidining tavsiya etilgan 4 l/ga va 6 l/ga me'yordagi eritmaları tuproqqa sepib o'rganilgan.

Tuproqqa gerbitsid sepishdan oldin kartoshka tuganaklarini ekilishi bilan birga tuproq yuzasining 3–4 sm chuqurligiga *C.chinensis* zarpechak urug'i sepilib Pivot 10 % s.e.k. gerbitsidi qo'llanilgan. Kartoshka hosilini yig'ishtirishdan oldin zarpechakni tarqalishi tajriba variantlarida 28,1, 7,7 va 7,3 % bo'lgan bo'lsa, bu ko'rsatkich etalonda 39,9 %, nazoratda esa 67,3 foizga teng bo'lgan. Kartoshka hosildorligi yuqorida qayd etilgan variantlarda 234, 246,5 va 248,1 s/ga ga, etalonda 212 s/ga va nazoratda uning hosili 170 s/ga bo'lganligi aniqlangan.

Piyozda zarpechakning tarqalishi Pivot 10 % s.e.k. sepilganda tajriba variantlarida 22,1, 10,9 va 10 foizga teng bo'lsa, etalonda 47,2 % va nazorat variantida 85 % bo'lganligi aniqlangan. Tajriba variantlarida hosildorlik 143, 148 va 150 s/ga, etalon va nazoratdagi hosildorlik 131 va 120 s/ga ni tashkil qilgan.

Sabzi hosilini yig'ishtirishdan oldin tajriba variantlarida zarpechakning tarqalishi 21,7, 6,3 va 6,2 %, etalonda 30,0 % va nazoratda 59,6 % bo'lgan. Sabzi hosili 208, 226 va 226,4 s/ga, etalonda 192 s/ga va nazoratda 183 s/ga bo'lgan.

Kichik tajriba maydonchalarida kartoshka, piyoz, sabzida parazitlik qiladigan zarpechak turlariga qarshi Pivot 10 % s.e.k. gerbitsidini 1,0 va 1,5 l/ga me'yorlarda qo'llash yaxshi samara berganligi qayd etilgan.

Ishlab chiqarish sharoitida yuqorida qayd etilgan ekin turlarida Pivot 10 % s.e.k. gerbitsidining samaradorligini o'rganish yuzasidan tajribalar Toshkent viloyatidagi "Mabgulrus", "Qurbon ota", "Irisboeva Xuri bog'i", "Bahor" kabi fermer xo'jaliklari dalalarida o'tkazildi. Ishlab chiqarish sharoitida ham Pivot 10 % s.e.k. gerbitsidini tajriba uchun olingan yuqoridagi har ikki sarf me'yori kartoshka, piyoz va sabzi ekilgan maydonlarda parazitlik qiladigan barcha zarpechak turlariga samarali ta'sir etgani aniqlangan.

Begona o'tlardagi zarpechakka qarshi Pivot 10 % s.e.k. gerbitsidining 0,2- 0,3 % va 0,4 foizli eritmalarining ta'sirini zarpechak bosgan dala chetlarida sinab ko'rildi. Pivot 10 % s.e.k. ning sinalgan barcha variantlari yaxshi natija bergan. Gerbitsidning 0,3 % va 0,4 % qo'llanilgan variantlari nazoratga nisbatan yaxshi natijalarni bergan, ularning samaradorligi 91,4 va 91,9 foizni tashkil etgan. Sarf me'yorini inobatga olib, dala atrofidagi begona o'tlardagi zarpechakka qarshi 0,3 foizli (0,9 l/ga) Pivot 10 % s.e.k. gerbitsidini ishlatish tavsiya etilgan.

XULOSA: O'tkazilgan kuzatuvlar hamda hisob - kitoblarning ko'rsatishicha Pivot 10 % s.e.k. gerbitsidini zarpechaklarga qarshi ishlatilganda kartoshkada rentabellik 58,4 % va sof daromad 3305925 so'm/ga, piyozda 115,8 % va 1556500 so'm/ga, sabzida 149,0 % va 2513500 so'm/ga bo'lganligi aniqlangan.

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